

Exploring New Dimensions in the *Phygital*

At the Intersection of Performance Art, Real-Time Installation, and Extended Realities.

Flavia Mazzanti
Immerea
Vienna Austria
flavia@immerea.com

Manuel Bonell
Immerea
Vienna Austria
manuel@immerea.com

ABSTRACT

“Beyond My Skin” (2022-2024) is an interdisciplinary research project presented in the forms of an interactive real time installation, hybrid performance, and MR (Mixed Reality) experience. By exploring the hybrid relationship between bodies and their digital representation in a posthuman context [1], the project creates a *phygital* (physical-digital) space where visitors can experience new dimensions of self-perception and interaction with others, in a constant interchange between physical and virtual worlds.

KEYWORDS

Hybrid performance, interactive installation, motion capture, real-time CG, mixed reality.

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1 Concept and Development

The starting point of the project lies in the understanding of the body as a non-binary and dynamic entity, whose essence is not defined by physical or social constructs but by its interaction and exchange with other beings [4]. Movement is seen here as a form of identity and self-expression, through which sensations and feelings can be transmitted and exchanged. The project combines the understanding of bodies with an experimental use of technology and immersive media to enable different perspectives and alternative representations of classical avatars in the digital space [3, 5]. In “Beyond My Skin” motion capture technology is used to dissolve and transform the physical appearance of the human body in real-time.

Here, four Kinect sensors, positioned at the corners of the physical space, record and transmit physical movements to the application running on a computer. These data are then transformed in real-time into digital animated configurations displayed on two large screens or projections. Two different perspectives are offered: a front view, which focuses more on the silhouettes and interaction between different bodies, and a top view, which emphasizes a further spatial level of abstraction.

Figure 1: Live Performance of “Beyond My Skin” at the Deep Space 8K, Ars Electronica Center, Linz, 2024.

Movements are recorded and translated into digital configurations, and multiple bodies merge into a collective hybrid body. This transformation affects not only the physical aspect of the body, but also its temporal and spatial changes. Actions, movements, and interactions overlap spatial and temporal boundaries, from which a new hybrid environment emerges. In this context, the combination of physical and digital environments plays a central role in creating a *phygital* world. Physical and digital are equally important here and neither can be seen without the other, both complementing each other in our perception and experience. This creates a balance between the two spaces and the third hybrid space they collectively generate.

On a technical level, two depth sensors (Azure Kinect) generate a real-time point-cloud silhouette of the bodies, while all four sensors create motion capture skeletons. These combined elements are used to represent the digital figures. Their parameters are related to the speed and fluidity of movements: the slower the movements, the clearer the figures become; the faster the movements, the more chaotic and harder to differentiate the visual structures become. Another important parameter is the virtual distance between the two figures: as the bodies move apart in physical space, they come closer together in the digital. In particular, there is a specific trigger moment when the digital bodies are close to each other, at which point the animation style changes from particles to lines to visualize this moment of contact and entanglement of the two bodies.

2 Performance, Installation, MR Experience

“Beyond My Skin” is a research project and installation, a place for constant exploration of different possibilities within the dynamic relationship between the human body and *phygital* realities. Comprising several interconnected layers, the project presents three primary formats to the public: a live hybrid performance featuring two professional dancers and accompanied by live sound; a real-time, interactive installation where visitors can interact with each other; and a MR experience.

2.1 Live Performance

The live performance showcases two professional dancers and is accompanied by live sound. The performance, lasting 20-25 minutes, has been conceptualized in collaboration with a choreographer, with a strong focus on the interaction between both bodies in the physical and digital realms. Differently from the interactive installation, which is open to be experimented by exhibition visitors, through the narrative character of the performance it is possible to transmit the artistic-philosophical vision of the project in a stronger way and to invite the audience to reflect and deepen their understandings of the project's themes and concepts.

2.2 Interactive *Phygital* Installation

The real-time, interactive installation invites visitors to engage with each other through abstract virtual bodies generated in real-time, exploring together the hybrid relationships between their physical selves and their digital representations. Within this immersive environment, physical interaction is transcended as visitors interact mostly through their abstract forms. Through virtual touches and overlaps, visitors merge into a shared hybrid entity, enabling new forms of movement and relationships. In this way, the interaction goes beyond the skin, beyond physical and social constructs, enabling a hybrid space centered on inclusion and exchange.

Figure 2: Interactive Installation, part of the group exhibition “Desert of Realities”, esc medien kunst labor, Graz, 2023. Lower photo © esc medien kunst labor, Martin Gross

2.3 MR Experience

The MR experience, completed in April 2024, is the latest layer of this interdisciplinary project, realized for the Meta Quest3 glasses. Here, visitors can see the virtual bodies of the performers, previously recorded, brought back to the physical environment. The experience creates a *phygital* space where both physical and virtual merge, adding an additional layer to this entangled exploration between both realms. Through temporal interventions in the city, there was the interest to bring these abstract, virtual figures – originated from the physical world – to different public spaces, questioning not only the boundaries between physical and virtual, but also between public and private spaces and forms of embodiment.

Figure 3: MR Experience. Series of interventions in public space, Vienna, 2024.

3 Interdisciplinary Approach

The project was developed by an interdisciplinary team of more than ten people coming from various fields and backgrounds, including media artists, designers, programmers, technical artists, performers, and sound designers. This enriching and diversified process made possible to approach development and find solutions from multiple perspectives, as well as to address new possibilities during the project's evolution.

4 Conclusion

The development of “Beyond My Skin” has been an exciting process, merging artistic vision with technical challenges and the possibility to constantly learn through the integration and exchange of various disciplines and technologies. Through its interdisciplinary approach and exploration at the intersection of physical and virtual realms, the project significantly contributes to the discourse on the relationship between art and technology. It aims to offer new perspectives on our existence in an ever-evolving technological landscape by exploring the intricate relationship between human beings and the world, both physical and digital, challenging traditional notions of materiality and embodiment from a posthuman perspective.

PROJECT CREDITS

A project by Flavia Mazzanti.
Produced by Immerea.

Concept and artistic direction: Flavia Mazzanti
Project Management: Design and Installation: Manuel Bonell
Choreography: Olivia Hild
Performance: Bitu Bell, Olivia Hild, Imani Rameses, Viviane Tanzmeister
Sound Design: Brootworth Technical
Artist: Tobias Mayer

Programming: Catherine Joy Calupas, Michael Bonell.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Rosi Braidotti, 2013. *The Posthuman*. Polity Press, Malden, USA.
- [2] Larry D. Busbea, 2020. *The Responsive Environment: Design, Aesthetics, and the Human in the 1970s*. University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, USA and London, UK.
- [3] Laura Guillaume and Joe Hughes, 2011. *Deleuze and the Body*. Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh, UK.
- [4] Donna Haraway, 2016. *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene*. Duke University Press Book, Durham and London, UK.
- [5] Gabriele Klein and Katharina Liebsch, 2022. *Ferne Körper: Berührung im digitalen Alltag*. Philipp Reclam jun. Verlag GmbH, Stuttgart, Germany.